

On the collaboration of the European AI-on-Demand Platform with key European AI Innovation initiatives; the case of European Digital Innovation Hubs and AI Factories

Position paper

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Abstract

The European Union (EU) has invested significantly in advancing artificial intelligence (AI) through a series of interrelated initiatives, including one-stop-shop projects such as the European Digital Innovation Hubs and the AI Factories and a flagship infrastructure development initiative, the AI-on-Demand Platform. This paper argues that fostering collaboration between these initiatives is essential to maximise their collective impact, encourage cross-fertilisation of activities, and strengthen Europe's AI ecosystem. We explore the collaboration dimensions, ranging from technical to business and knowledge-oriented, highlighting the identified pathways and their prospective benefits for the involved initiatives. Subsequently, we identify some of the challenges for the implementation of the pathways and present indicative customer journeys where the EU initiatives use the Platform as part of their service offering. Finally, we provide some strategic recommendations that would enable the adoption of the pathways and address the challenges. The findings aim to guide policymakers and initiative leaders in shaping a more interconnected and effective AI landscape where synergies allow the cross-fertilisation of individual activities funded by the EU.

Introduction

The EU Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL)¹ seeks to integrate digital technologies into businesses, public administrations, and society, with Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a key focus. Two pivotal initiatives within this effort are the European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) and the European AI-on-Demand Platform (AIoDP). Moreover, the European Commission (EC) has launched the AI Innovation Package to support AI startups and SMEs, which includes the set-up of the European AI Factories as one of its pillars. These initiatives fall under the supervision of the EC AI Office, which aims to enable the future development, deployment and use of AI in a way that fosters societal and economic benefits and innovation while mitigating risks. An overview of these initiatives, the role of the AI Office and the background work is provided below.

The European AI-on-Demand Platform

DeployAI project², which started in January 2024 stands at the cutting edge of industrial AI innovation, building the next-generation European AIoDP. This platform³ aims to democratise access to AI resources, empowering businesses (in particular SMEs and public administrations) across Europe to:

- Access ready-to-use AI tools, datasets, and services tailored for industrial applications through a development environment that will facilitate innovation and a marketplace that will allow the commercialisation and uptake of trustworthy AI solutions made in the EU.
- Enable and stimulate collaborations by mapping and connecting AI innovation stakeholders (from startups to investors, academia and other national and EU initiatives).

The project is therefore expected to establish links with the network of European Digital Innovation Hubs to provide SMEs and the public administration throughout Europe with access to AI tools and a governance mechanism for the future sustainability of the AIoDP.

The European Digital Innovation Hubs

The European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs)⁴ support companies to improve business/production processes, products, or services using digital technologies by providing one-stop-shop regional access to technical expertise and testing facilities as well as innovation services, such as financing advice, training, and skills development that are central to successful digital transformation. The services for start-ups, SMEs and public organisations are subsidised and therefore typically free of charge through the DIGITAL funding. The first restricted call for EDIHs has been completed with 136 projects chosen and most hubs becoming

¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/activities/digital-programme>

² <https://www.deployaiproject.eu/>

³ <https://www.aiodp.ai/>

⁴ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/activities/edihs>

operational since January 2023. A second call was launched to supplement the selection of EDIHs and to fill the gaps in the Network which resulted in the selection of a further 15 hubs that became operational by mid-2023. High-quality candidate EDIHs, for which no DIGITAL funding was available, have received a Seal of Excellence and got funded by their Member States or other sources and became part of the network of EDIHs. Furthermore, the “Digital Transformation Accelerator” (DTA) Call for Tenders⁵ was launched as a next step to support the EC in the deployment of a network of European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH network⁶) and in fostering networking, collaboration and knowledge transfer activities.

The European AI Factories

AI Factories (AIFs) initiative⁷ aims to strengthen Europe's capabilities in the field of AI and High-Performance Computing (HPC) by supporting the creation of ecosystems/hubs that promote innovation, collaboration and growth. They bring together computing power, data and talent as necessary elements to create groundbreaking Generative AI models and advance AI applications in various critical sectors. This initiative, highlighted in the political guidelines of Commission President Ursula von der Leyen, aims to turn Europe into the "AI continent". As the President stated in a recent speech⁸ “We have set up a record of 12 AI factories in just a few months. 7 are already up and running and the other 5 in the making. This is actually the largest public investment in AI in the world and our intention is that it seeds and multiplies.” The first 7 AIFs will begin their implementation work in April 2025.

The European AI Office

The European AI Office⁹ was established within the European Commission as the centre of AI expertise and forms the foundation for a single European AI governance system. It plays a key role in implementing the AI Act, enforces the rules for general-purpose AI models and promotes an innovative ecosystem of trustworthy AI, to reap the societal and economic benefits. It ensures a strategic, coherent and effective European approach to AI at the international level, becoming a global reference point. The “AI Innovation and Policy Coordination” unit (CONNECT.A.4) within the AI Office oversees the implementation of the EDIHs and the AIoDP DIGITAL initiatives.

Background work

The Pre-PAI project¹⁰ under DIGITAL realised the "Preparatory actions for the AI-on-demand platform" providing the blueprint for the further development, deployment and operation of the AIoDP. The project conducted a comprehensive requirement analysis for different stakeholder

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/tender-details/7791>

⁶ <https://european-digital-innovation-hubs.ec.europa.eu/home>

⁷ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/ai-factories>

⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/speech_25_463

⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/ai-office>

¹⁰ <https://www.ai4europe.eu/ai-community/projects/pre-pai>

groups, mainly SMEs, industrial sectors, public administration, (E)DIHs and the European Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs)¹¹.

Regarding the (E)DIHs, the following expectations from the AIoDP were expressed (we hereby summarise the most prevalent ones):

- Connection and networking opportunities with the AI ecosystem, TEFs and Data Spaces¹²
- Access to reliable data
- Secure access to HPC, cloud and edge infrastructures
- Training tools, including peer learning and training on trustworthy AI and AI regulations
- Support in the development of an AI adoption roadmap for SMEs
- Support in the implementation of their test-before-invest services
- Ready-to-use AI tools and resources for practical applications
- Trustworthiness assessment of their AI solutions
- Access to success stories, best practices, quality assurance methodologies and guidelines

The limitations of these consultations were that they lasted only for a few months when the EDIHs had just started operating and most of the stakeholders analysed were DIHs (EC's predecessor initiative¹³), both AI-aware and AI-unaware. Another bias may result from the fact that they had to respond to close-ended questions regarding the functionalities of a platform that they were not thoroughly informed on its purpose, therefore getting "guidance" from the survey's predefined closed-ended questions in what they should expect to see.

Scope of this paper

In this paper, we have chosen to elaborate on the collaboration with the EDIHs and AIFs as both initiatives act as one-stop shops for the industry and public administration, enabling AI-powered digital transformation. The client-facing role of these initiatives enables both technical and business development opportunities for the AIoDP with a much broader outreach than the rest of the major EU initiatives which may suggest a higher level of prioritisation of such collaborations. Moreover, the authors' core involvement in these initiatives (as well as in the AIoDP) provides "hands-on" experience in the aspects we explore.

This paper argues that fostering collaboration between these initiatives and the AIoDP is essential to maximise their collective impact, encourage cross-fertilisation of activities, and strengthen Europe's AI ecosystem. By examining different dimensions, the following sections explore collaboration pathways, identify challenges, explore use cases and provide recommendations to policymakers and initiative leaders to enhance collaboration.

¹¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/testing-and-experimentation-facilities>

¹² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>

¹³

<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/digital-innovation-hubs-helping-companies-across-economy-make-most-digital-opportunities-brochure>

Collaboration Pathways

Collaboration between EU-funded AI initiatives is essential for avoiding duplication of efforts, increasing efficiency, and creating a multiplier effect for investments. By integrating their resources, expertise, and networks, these initiatives can enhance the accessibility and adoption of AI solutions across Europe. This section outlines key technical, business and knowledge/skills-oriented collaboration pathways that can drive synergies and innovation. These pathways are indicative yet not exhaustive suggestions.

Technical-oriented Collaboration

A technical-oriented collaboration can be accomplished in various ways. In the following list, we have identified those that are particularly useful in the collaboration of the EDIHs and AIFs with the AIoDP initiative and explain the associated benefits which apart from technical present significant business value for all stakeholders.

Pathway1. Design and deploy AI applications by assembling reusable AI modules into AI pipelines using the AIoDP AI Builder.

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: The platform will facilitate the creation of AI demos with minimal or no coding expertise that will entice and engage their clients. The EDIHs and AIFs can also train their clients' technical personnel on using the AI Builder as part of their service offering to support the continuation and ensure the sustainability of their AI adoption efforts. The initiatives can also upload useful AI modules to enhance the AI Builder and increase the visibility of their developments and expertise.
- Benefits for AIoDP: The use of the AI Builder will be increased and there will be opportunities for integration of external components developed and made available by the users. This will allow the platform to evolve into a sustainable, future-proof, competitive platform that facilitates AI solutions development.

Pathway2. Publish and access datasets, tools, models and services through the AIoDP Marketplace. Integration of those assets is facilitated by ontology-based metadata, which enables API access and effective retrieval.

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: Publishing their resources, assets and services at the Marketplace will increase the visibility of the activities performed by the initiatives, and the reuse of their components. Accessing components already available on the Marketplace can provide complementary expertise and tools to the initiatives, facilitating or enhancing their service development process or overall offering. The business-side benefits are mentioned in the respective section.
- Benefits for AIoDP: By growing its product portfolio with new assets, AIoDP will remain both technically and business-competitive and attract more potential

users. The reuse of the existing portfolio will increase the user database and return on investment (ROI) for its development.

Pathway3. Access and compare LLMs through the products available in the Marketplace. The initiatives and especially AIFs can additionally publish the LLMs that they will develop.

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: A growing number of clients is expected to request products and services that involve the use of LLMs. Accessing and/or comparing LLMs can help them serve those needs and stay relevant to technological developments, minimising time or investment for experimentation. In particular, the support of European LLMs that will be gradually provided by the AIoDP will be essential for targeted regional support. Hosting the AIFs-developed LLMs on the AIoDP will provide outreach beyond the ecosystems that they serve and allow their commercialisation for long-term sustainability.
- Benefits for AIoDP: Apart from getting its products used by a growing number of users, the AIoDP will be the platform/marketplace where new (European) LLMs are tested and commercialised, which will offer Pan-European visibility and significance and allow the respective technical communities exchange their expertise in a single point of reference.

Pathway4. Access Dataspaces through AIoDP connectors. “Dataspaces ensure that more data becomes available for use in the economy and society while keeping companies and individuals who generate the data in control.”¹⁴

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: Data is a crucial resource for developing AI applications. Providing connectors to other European initiatives such as the Common European Dataspaces or even privately handled dataspaces will facilitate their access to data. Moreover, most AIFs will develop Dataspaces to which the AIoDP can provide access, taking into account the respective policies.
- Benefits for AIoDP: AIoDP will offer access to trusted data assets that are essential for AI developments becoming the platform of choice for both data and technical tools for the EU initiatives and their clients.

Pathway5. Access HPC or Cloud resources essential for AI services development through AIoDP connectors.

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: EDIHs and AIFs might require HPC or Cloud resources either not available through the partners of the initiatives or in case they need to expand their capacity. AIoDP can provide easy access to (additional) HPC or Cloud resources for efficient and scalable model training and inference.
- Benefits for AIoDP: AIFs (and some EDIHs) may also be able to provide HPC and Cloud capacity to external users and the AIoDP (through its connectors) can

¹⁴ <https://dataspaces.info/common-european-data-spaces/#page-content>

provide central access to these distributed resources being a single point of reference for easy access to HPC and Cloud resources in Europe.

Pathway6. Access various key EU initiatives such as the European Data Space-related: SIMPL (Cloud-to-edge federations empowering EU data spaces), GAIA-X (European Association for Data and Cloud AISBL), Copernicus (EU's Earth Observation), EOSC (European Open Science Cloud), the TEFs and other initiatives or repositories.

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: Exploiting those connectors can facilitate networking and collaboration activities with key European initiatives and assets.
- Benefits for AIoDP: AIoDP can be the main inclusive place where the EU initiatives and AI-related communities connect and interact fulfilling one of its core missions.

Business/Ecosystem-oriented collaboration

The business and ecosystem-oriented collaboration pathways depend, in some cases, on the successful technical collaboration and aim to further contribute to value creation and complementarity of the EU initiatives.

Pathway7. Utilise the AIoDP Marketplace, which facilitates trading and practical use of AI products and connects AI providers and consumers, to acquire or publish AI assets, increasing reusability and visibility and reducing time-to-market.

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: EDIHs and AIFs that publish their outcomes on the Marketplace can expand the outreach of both hubs and clients and enable the commercialisation of the respective solutions. This can assist the long-term sustainability of the initiatives (beyond their EU & Member State funding period) and the support they provide. Moreover, EDIHs and AIFs can find a series of services in the Marketplace, including domain-specific pre-built AI solutions that can bootstrap their developments. Additionally, these collaborations can be published as success stories to increase visibility and guide less mature AI adopters with their use cases.
- Benefits for AIoDP: These collaborations will expand the offerings of the AIoDP with tailored AI solutions (across industry verticals and regional needs) provided by the EU initiatives and/or their clients, creating a competitive European Marketplace with diverse offerings and facilitating the exchange of AI products across borders.

Pathway8. Use the AIoDP Business Navigator (formerly proposed as Interactive Landscape Tool), a tool that allows users to explore the AI ecosystem and get insights into available AI resources and entities across Europe. This tool incorporated data visualisation search and filter functionalities as well as market intelligence and analytics.

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: Through the Navigator, EDIHs and AIFs can find potential clients or collaborators with AI expertise and assist their business

development and networking activities. EDIHs and AIFs can register in the Navigator and get discoverable themselves.

- Benefits for AIoDP: AIoDP aims to include a comprehensive view of the EU AI Landscape, yet gathering and updating this information is cumbersome. The EDIHs and AIFs can encourage their clients to register their information in the Navigator and get discoverable, enriching this landscape with stakeholders from their regional outreach and updated insights.

Pathway9. Leverage the respective ecosystems for competitive and sustainable growth.

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: EDIHs and AIFs can bring their ecosystem needs to the AIoDP management team to drive future developments, tailored to their needs, which will have increased business and societal impact.
- Benefits for AIoDP: AIoDP needs to develop channels to reach national and regional stakeholders. EDIHs and AIFs focus on and serve such ecosystems and can act as intermediaries/ambassadors for the AIoDP. Moreover, the EDIHs' and AIFs' SME and public service networks can act as early adopters of AIoDP services and bring their assets (tools, use cases, etc.) to enrich the AIoDP marketplace.

Pathway10. Exploit the AIoDP Matchmaking Tool which matches the needs and desires of the user to stakeholders, resources, products and services using metadata.

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: EDIHs and AIFs along with their customers can profit from targeted networking with relevant AI resources, expertise, and opportunities based on their specific needs and interests.
- Benefits for AIoDP: The initiatives can register their resources and increase the matching accuracy and capacity of the tool.

Pathway11. Access AIoDP Trustworthiness Assessment services focused on evaluating, ensuring, and promoting the trustworthiness of AI resources

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: The initiatives and their customers can easily assess their resources and developments compliance with the AI Act and other regulations and ethical/legal aspects.
- Benefits for AIoDP: Providing these services is a competitive advantage for onboarding users in the AIoDP, as compliance with the AI Act is mandatory for AI applications developed and used in the EU. Early adopters of the services that are part of the EU ecosystem will provide valuable feedback towards improving those services.

Pathway12. Explore synergies through the AIoDP Partner Program to shape strategic collaborations that include benefits for strategic partners and early on-boarding.

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: The Partner Program strategy and associated benefits will engage the respective initiatives in more targeted and long-term collaboration.

- Benefits for AIoDP: The AIoDP will profit from having EDIHs and AIFs among its strategic partners, not only because of the synergies created among EU initiatives but also because they will help the platform reach their large national or regional ecosystems.

Pathway13. Exploit and promote DeployAI's Open Calls that aim to showcase and increase the uptake of the AIoDP platform and tools across various use cases.

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: The promotion of the Open Calls (OCs) to their ecosystems can be considered as a part of the “Support to Find Investment” pillar of EDIHs or the Business Support of AIFs and help increase the funding opportunities available for the SMEs to scale or continue their innovation efforts.
- Benefits for AIoDP: The OCs will reach a larger audience with minimum effort from the AIoDP stakeholders as long as the initiatives are engaged (see also Pathway9). This can lead to getting more competitive and diverse proposals and more impactful outcomes from the funded projects.

Pathway14. Participate in networking and ecosystem-building activities, such as the participation in thematic/networking events organised by one of the initiatives or the EC or through the (co-)organisation of joint events that will bring together the AI ecosystem and the communities that want to interact with it.

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: By participating in events organised by the DeployAI project or the EC, they will have the opportunity to network and increase synergies that will benefit their clients as well as their understanding of the AIoDP developments.
- Benefits for AIoDP: With the participation in events organised by the initiatives or their respective coordination actions or the EC, the AIoDP stakeholders will have the opportunities to interact, connect and exploit value-adding networking opportunities. Joint events are also encouraged to increase the engagement.

Knowledge and skills exchange

This paragraph contains collaboration pathways related to knowledge and skills exchange.

Pathway15. Exploit the training programs and educational resources on AI technologies and best practices/success stories available on the AIoDP. Moreover, the initiatives or their coordination actions (e.g. the DTA-EDIH Network) can incorporate their own relevant material

- Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs: The initiatives can leverage the material that will be available on the AIoDP (produced by DeployAI, the predecessor project AI4Europe¹⁵ as well as material incorporated from other sources such as EuroCC¹⁶) to enrich their training offering to their clients. They may also make

¹⁵ <https://ai4europe.aiod.eu/>

¹⁶ https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/research-innovation/our-projects/eurocc_en

available through the AIoDP their own training material, best practices and success stories to increase outreach.

- **Benefits for AIoDP:** By incorporating the material of relevant AI initiatives that will complement the one developed by the DeployAI project, the AIoDP will have the essential capacity to act as a hub for talent nurturing and AI adoption acceleration in Europe.

Pathway16. Access AI expertise that will facilitate AI developments.

- **Benefits for EDIHs and AIFs:** External experts registered at the AIoDP can be leveraged for consulting sessions with the EDIHs and AIFs and their customers. This is particularly useful for EDIHs with lower AI readiness or for both initiatives when they have limited capacity or need to deliver services that are beyond their expertise.
- **Benefits for AIoDP:** EDIHs and AIFs experts can be exploited by the AIoDP and connected with users that need support through the Matchmaking Tool or networking activities and therefore increase its pool of experts.

Challenges

Despite the potential benefits of collaboration, several barriers hinder seamless cooperation between EU AI initiatives. These challenges range from structural and financial limitations to technical and governance-related obstacles. Addressing these challenges is essential to unlock the full potential of AI collaboration in Europe.

Challenge1. Misalignment in relevant Work Programmes

The EU AI Initiatives under consideration have been launched in different timeframes under different work programmes, although the intention was the one that was succeeding (AIoDP and then AIFs) to involve activities that would serve the other ones (i.e. AIoDP to involve activities with EDIHs and AIFs to involve activities with AIoDP and EDIHs). Therefore, this misalignment in the (existing) grant agreements and funding allocation priorities creates operational inconsistencies across initiatives. Moreover, while the EDIHs and AIoDP are implemented through the DIGITAL under the supervision of CONNECT.A.4, AIFs services are implemented through HORIZON under the supervision of the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC), which would require coordination among the supervising authorities.

Challenge2. Varying timeframes for project implementation

This timing misalignment might hinder synchronized collaboration. For example, most AIFs will be operational by the end of 2025 – beginning of 2026, when the AIoDP will be already operating for almost two years, which presents both opportunities (e.g. maturity

of the platform) and challenges (e.g. less time to explore collaboration pathways or for stakeholder needs assessment and consideration in the development). Furthermore, the EDIHs won't be eager to engage in new activities in 2025 which is (in most cases) the last year of their funding and still have other KPIs to meet, while, during this year, they need to submit their proposals for the next funding round (Work Programme 2025).

Challenge3. Lack of financial and strategic incentives

The lack of clear incentives in the existing Work Programmes discourages active engagement between initiatives. For example:

- EDIHs were not required to collaborate with the AIoDP to achieve shared goals through their respective Funding Calls/Grant Agreements
- AI Factories were requested to provide a networking plan with the AIoDP, which does not force/dictate meaningful collaboration in more technical or business aspects
- The AIoDP had foreseen interoperability with the EDIHs but assumed that it would have been possible in a uniform technical way.
- The coordination action of the EDIHs (DTA-EDIH Network) is supposed to support mainly/only knowledge transfer activities (such as “train the trainer”) with the AIoDP being among a list of various other DIGITAL initiatives and without a specific mandate in the relevant tender, which prevents a more targeted and diverse engagement.
- Resource constraints of the initiatives push them to balance human effort with the available funding which has already been assigned to other activities.

Challenge4. Technical interoperability

The varying implementation models across EDIHs and AIFs pose challenges in implementing technical interoperability (with the strict definition of the word). For example, the large number of EDIHs and their non-uniform way of operation and service delivery, which depend on the implementation roadmap proposed uniquely by each one, prevent a one-size-fits-all approach to technical interoperability.

Challenge5. Governance and compliance complexities

EDIHs and AIFs are co-funded by the Member States (50% DIGITAL, 50% national funding). The national funding rules might complicate cross-border collaboration. In particular, EDIHs could not achieve their targets for serving companies of other EU countries, which were countersigned through cross-border collaborations with other EDIHs, due to the applicable national funding rules.

Challenge6. IP issues

EDIHs and AIFs develop tailored services for their clients. In most cases, the respective contracts mandate that the foreground IP rights belong to the client, which prevents

publishing them in the AIoDP marketplace or as a success story for example, without the consent of the client.

Challenge7. Who pays the price?

AIoDP is planned to act as a commercial platform. To ensure long-term viability, its products will have an associated cost (at least some of them and likely most of them after the DIGITAL funding ends). Therefore, a question arises on how would the EDIHs and AIFs pay for the use of the AIoDP assets to complement their developments.

Use Cases

As an exercise where we could see in practice how the EU initiatives (AIFs and EDIHs) would use the AIoDP, we created a canvas with the AIoDP high-level offering and shared it with DeployAI partners that are involved in those initiatives (Demokritos for Pharos AI Factory and Smart Attica EDIH, CSC for LUMI AI Factory and HubFrance for a French EDIH). The partners created indicative customer journeys based on their operation model and combined their offerings with that of the AIoDP as depicted in the following paragraph.

Indicative Customer Journeys

The canvas and customer journeys are provided in the [Appendix](#) in landscape orientation to improve readability.

Remarks

This exercise provided some valuable insights into how would EDIHs and AIFs see the interaction with the AIoDP summarised below:

Common elements:

- The AIoDP development tools and marketplace assets would be beneficial for their service development (incl. success stories, datasets, etc.).
- The Business Navigator and Matchmaking tools can help their business development and networking efforts.
- The Marketplace can increase the visibility and commercialisation of the Initiatives' as well as their clients' developments and outcomes.
- Training modules would be appreciated to be combined with their offerings.
- Compliance and trustworthiness services would be leveraged.

Key differences:

- Pharos AIF and Smart Attica EDIH would like to use AIoDP training material to raise awareness at an early stage, while LUMI would rely first on its resources.
- Smart Attica EDIH would leverage the AIoDP for feasibility assessment (e.g. the AI Builder for demo creation that would entice customers and the LLM playground to compare LLMs).
- The French EDIH would use the Marketplace to create a service offering for its clients and let the mature ones explore it themselves.
- LUMI would exploit its own Trustworthiness module at an early stage.

We need to mention that engaging the project partners showed more optimistic results than the ones we would have obtained by opening the exercise to AIFs and EDIHs not participating in DeployAI. However, we needed to provide examples and a roadmap for the rest who would have less understanding and would be more reluctant to engage in the exercise and interact

with the AIoDP in general. Overall, this brainstorming exercise allowed the identification of potential interactions not yet considered by current AIoDP customer journeys already prepared by DeployAI and could guide future developments.

Recommendations

To facilitate meaningful collaboration among AI initiatives, targeted policy interventions, strategic alignment, and technical solutions must be implemented. This section provides some concrete recommendations to address the identified challenges and promote sustainable cooperation. An important principle is that collaboration should not be forced and that in the end will be driven by value creation. However, as AI progress is exponential, the timeframe for EU initiatives to remain relevant is quite limited, demanding more critical interventions.

For EU initiative managers

Recommendation1. Explore the collaboration pathways outlined in this paper, choose the ones that better fit the respective EU initiative needs and get in touch with the AIoDP managers to initiate collaboration discussions or directly access the relevant resources and opportunities.

Recommendation2. Suggest or finetune collaboration pathways that address their specific initiative needs and challenges and are more aligned with their operations. They should see the AIoDP as an opportunity to support their development and engage in collaboration and networking activities.

For the AIoDP managers

Recommendation3. Organise tailored training sessions regularly to keep the initiatives up-to-date with the platform releases and allow its full utilisation. The AIoDP offerings should be clear to EDIHs and AIFs. For the EDIHs, such training sessions can be co-organised with the DTA-EDIH network managers.

Recommendation4. Provide technical specifications and support (through guides or direct consultations to their coordination actions) to facilitate interoperability with the AIoDP. The AIoDP should pave the way for the development of targeted/universal connectors with other EU initiatives after consultations with the relevant stakeholders. If such developments do not fit into the current work plan, timely actions should be taken to initiate discussions with the supervising authorities on how to proceed.

Recommendation5. Orchestrate bilateral meetings with the EU initiatives that are part of the consortium or with direct connections, such as those involved in the Customer Journeys exercise, to engage them in the interoperability activities and get targeted feedback on the AIoDP current and planned offerings.

Recommendation6. Expand the stakeholder needs assessment surveys to EDIHs, AIFs, and other initiatives with the support of their Coordination Actions (such as the DTA-EDIH network) or through direct connections. The content of these surveys has to be internally coordinated both on the technical and business sides to align with the strategy and planned activities.

Recommendation7. Provide a sustainable partnership scheme to incentivise collaboration with other EU initiatives. For example, by publishing non-commercial assets on the AIoDP, the initiatives could get credits that could be exchanged for commercial offerings. This could be part of the AIoDP business plan tailored to EU initiatives.

For the supervising authorities (AI Office & EUROHPC officers)

These recommendations could be implemented through the EDIHs, AIFs, DeployAI (current or future) work plans or relevant Coordination Actions or included in new calls for projects or tenders.

Recommendation8. Require or incentivise EDIHs and AIFs to upload at least a portion of their developments (datasets, tools, models and services) to the AIoDP Marketplace through their respective Work Programmes and Agreements.

Recommendation9. Incentivise the agreement of EDIHs and AIFs clients to provide the outcomes of the services they get commercially through the Marketplace and publish them as success stories. Provide advice and protection regarding the IP issues/concerns that might arise.

Recommendation10. Ensure that some of the AIoDP assets and functionalities will be available for free or subsidised for use by the other EU initiatives at least for as long as the EU funding lasts.

Recommendation11. Strengthen partnerships between the AIoDP and the Coordination Actions, such as the DTA-EDIH Network, to enable dynamic data sharing and engagement in joint activities. The DTA-EDIH Network contains valuable information that could feed the AIoDP tools (such as the Business Navigator and the Matchmaking Tool) in an automatic way through the development of relevant API access mechanisms, as long as this is supported by the relevant platform. The follow-up work programme for the DTA-EDIH Network should include the necessary provisions. Examples of information that would be beneficial to be retrieved are: the profiles and list of services that the EDIHs offer to showcase their basic information and expertise, the success stories and lessons learnt that they have published, etc. Moreover, the EDIHs' clients could optionally give their consent to publish some of the information they register on the Tools to increase their visibility and matchmaking opportunities. A similar approach should be followed by a potential Coordination Action of the AIFs.

Recommendation12. Resolve operational, governance and compliance inconsistencies among the initiatives and create a coordination group with representatives of their supervising authorities. If the current Actions and Work plans cannot overcome the challenges and modify their operational planning, a new or follow-up Action would be more fit for the purpose.

Recommendation13. Propose targeted cross-domain and perhaps cross-initiative Working Groups that will put in force and oversee the collaboration activities and foresee participation and representation of the respective initiatives. This might be one of the roles of a potential new or follow-up Action.

Recommendation14. Encourage collaboration between initiatives through Open Calls (Financial Support to Third Parties scheme) either in DeployAI or future Work Programmes. An example would be asking third parties to combine services received by more than one of those initiatives to implement their project proposal, e.g. combine AIoDP tools and EDIH services. This would provide real success stories to encourage further collaboration and showcase how the initiatives could offer complementarities.

Conclusion

Collaboration between EU AI initiatives is key to maximising investments and fostering a robust AI ecosystem and can be accomplished in various ways, from technical to business and knowledge-related as outlined in this paper along with the resulting benefits of its pathway. By addressing the associated challenges that we have presented, the EU can create a more cohesive, effective, and innovative AI landscape. The recommendations outlined in this paper aim to drive sustainable collaboration, ensuring that Europe remains at the forefront of AI advancements and that the financial instruments provide the maximum return on investment.

Although this paper has focused on the potential collaboration of the AI-on-Demand Platform with the European Digital Innovation Hubs and the AI Factories, where the authors are actively involved, a similar approach could also be followed for other initiatives. For example, the Testing and Experimentation Facilities have a similar service-oriented approach, yet with a more sectorial focus, therefore, the collaboration pathways are quite similar. The Common European Data Spaces will need a different technical approach although the principle of agreeing to universal connectors still holds and the ontology-based architecture of the Platform facilitates the interoperability. The challenges and recommendations are applicable to most EU-funded initiatives can be easily adjusted after consultations with the respective stakeholders under the supervision and guidance of the AI Office.

Appendix - Customer Journeys

AIoDP high-level offering

Pharos AI Factory | Customer: SME | Use case: Energy demand forecast

LUMI AI Factory | Customer SME | Use case: Smart Manufacturing system

The AIoDP will provide AI Factory customer with:

- Facilitation of its technical growth
- Compliance
- Networking
- Increased outreach, visibility and recognition (EU and beyond)

miro

Smart Attica EDIH | Customer: Municipality | Use case: LLM chatbot for employees & citizens

French EDIH | Customer: Generic | Use case: Generic

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Files Repository

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